

Preparative Thin-layer Chromatographic Separation of Some Isomeric Chalcone-Flavanone Mixtures

DURGA NATH DHAR

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur-16 (U.P.), India

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In the synthesis of some 2',4'-dihydroxychalcones by the Claisen-Schmidt reaction, we also isolated small amounts of the isomeric 7-hydroxyflavanones¹. The separation of the chalcone-flavanone mixture presented a problem and recourse had to be taken to fractional crystallization—a procedure which is time consuming and wasteful and even then the chalcone which separated was contaminated with the traces of the corresponding flavanone. We have now successfully adopted the technique of preparative thin-layer chromatography in effecting this separation. We find this method of choice in terms of simplicity of operation, cleanness in separation and economy in time and material. This method was tried on eight chalcone-flavanone mixtures, prepared for the purpose, and found to give satisfactory separations (exception: Compounds XIII and XIV in combination). The preparative TLC was carried out on silica gel, using petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (2 : 1) as the developer solvent system (ascending). The visualisation of the flavanones was effected by a short exposure of the chromatogram to iodine vapours. The chromatographic data of these compounds are presented in Table I.

TABLE I

Chromatographic data of some 2',4'-dihydroxychalcones and 7-hydroxyflavanones*

Compd. No.	2',4'-dihydroxychalcones	R _f (× 100)	Compd. No.	7-Hydroxyflavanones	R _f (× 100)
I	R = 2—Cl	52	II	R = 2'—Cl	43
III	R = 3—Cl	53	IV	R = 3'—Cl	44
V	R = 4—Cl	52	VI	R = 4'—Cl	43
VII	R = 3—Me	54	VIII	R = 3'—Me	44
IX	R = 4—Me	57	X	R = 4'—Me	46
XI	R = 3—NO ₂	56	XII	R = 3'—NO ₂	45
XIII	R = 2,3—(OCH ₃) ₂	49	XIV	R = 2',3'—(OCH ₃) ₂	48
XV	R = 3—OCH ₃ ,4—OH	48	XVI	R = 3—OCH ₃ ,4—OH	30

* Obtained in a separate experiment. R_f-values were determined on glass plate, 20×10 cm, each coated with 3.3 g silica gel. Other experimental details were the same as described for the preparative TLC (vide infra).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The polyhydroxychalcones^{1,2} were synthesized by the Claisen-Schmidt reaction of resacetophenone with isomeric chlorobenzaldehydes, *m*- and *p*-tolualdehydes, *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde, 2,3-dimethoxybenzaldehyde and vanillin, in presence of aqueous-alcoholic potassium hydroxide.

The chalcones, prepared as outlined above, were then cyclized to the corresponding flavanones¹ with 4% aqueous-alcoholic sulphuric acid.

Mixtures of various isomeric chalcone-flavanone (1 : 1) were prepared (for example : compounds I-II; III-IV; V-VI etc.) and separated by preparative TLC as described below.

Preparative TLC : Silica gel, E. Merck A.G., Darmstadt (Germany) was used and applied as a suspension in water onto a glass plate, 20 × 20 cm., by means of 'Desaga' spreader. The compounds were applied to the TLC plate as bands in the usual manner³. Other details about visualization of separated zones and their collection for subsequent extraction were similar to those described in literature³.

R E F E R E N C E S

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3. E. Stahl, Editor, "Thin-layer Chromatography", English Translation, Springer-Verlag, New York Inc. (1969), pp. 97—105.